

INTRODUCTION

To date, machine learning researchers have tended to approach the issue of concept formation and exemplar selection tasks by presenting a pre-selected set of multiattribute cases to a learning algorithm and then examining the success with which the machine has learned the concept (EXAMPLE). Variations on this general approach include the introduction of noise into the data (EXAMPLE), incremental learning via genetic algorithms (Davis, 1987), or incremental learning via recursive partitioning algorithms (Utgoff, 1988; Crawford, 1989). This basic learning paradigm is presented in Figure 1.

Insert Figure 1 About Here

The feature of that paradigm which is germane to this paper is that the cases submitted to the learning algorithm are selected *a priori* by the researchers, either from some pre-existing database or from a database specially constructed. On the other hand, one learning paradigm which appears not to have been examined previously in the machine learning literature is Self Guided Learning (SeGuL) (Reidpath & Diamond, 1992; Bruner, 1956). SeGuL is iterative, where a learner generates a rule (R_n) for selecting a positive case on iteration $n+1$. The rule is generated on the basis of the cases previously selected by rules $R_1 \dots R_{n-1}$ (see Figure 2). In a SeGuL paradigm the cases which will be submitted to the learner could not be known *a priori*, because it is the learner which selects the new case at each iteration.

Insert Figure 2 About Here

In terms of optimum learning this paradigm appears to have little to commend it. The self guided nature of the case selection means that terrible bias could enter the positive case list which is used in the inductive learning (Reidpath & Diamond, 1992). Indeed, Brehmer (1980) argued that this type of bias was instrumental in preventing humans from obtaining a veridical perception of reality. Notwithstanding these difficulties, there are a number of instances in which humans appear to employ this learning paradigm, and they employ it because their aim is not to obtain a veridical perception of reality, but to select cases which possess a particular attribute. For example, an insurance fraud investigator who must select claims to investigate. The investigator has to screen thousands of insurance claims in order to select the few claims which his limited resources will allow him to investigate (see Reidpath, 1992). His job requires him, in every instance, to select claims which he believes constitute a fraud. He selects a claimant to investigate and, on the basis of the results of that investigation, adjusts the "algorithm" by which he selects the next claimant to investigate. He continues this

process *ad infinitum*, always keeping in mind that he cannot afford to waste time selecting claimants who are not defrauding the insurance company. Other examples of SeGuL include selecting the best students for admission into a graduate program, selecting the best job applicant for an employment vacancy, and traiging patients in a hospital emergency department.

The aim of this study was to develop a machine implementation of SeGuL. In this instance by employing a simple statistically based learning algorithm -- linear regression (Bowerman, O'Connel, & Dickey, 1986). Since the demonstrated failure of the perceptron to cope with linearly inseparable logical XOR data-sets (Minsky, and Papert, 1969) machine learning theorists have largely ignored linear modeling techniques as an approach to machine learning. This notwithstanding the success of linear models at modeling human judgement in a wide range of tasks (LOTS OF REFERENCES). This study could equally have used any other induction algorithm in its stead, since the critical feature of the SeGuL paradigm is the selection of positive cases, and not the resolution of the structure underlying the data.

METHOD

Outline

The learner was initialised with a rule (R_0), and with a list (L) of randomly selected cases. Each iteration (i), beginning with $i = 0$, of the learning process comprised the following steps:

- Step 1. Read the next five available cases from a database.
- Step 2. Use rule R_i to select from the five current cases the case most likely to be a positive case.
- Step 3. Add the selected case to list L .
- Step 4. Construct a new rule R_{i+1} from list L .
- Step 5. Increment i .

The various parts of the algorithm are discussed in the four successive subsections. These are followed by a subsection describing the actual databases examined in this paper, and another subsection detailing the initial conditions of the algorithm.

Definition of a Case

A case C was defined as a vector of six real valued attributes $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_6$ and a dichotomous criterion y . The values for each of the six attributes were generated by a pseudo-random number generator. These were normally distributed (mean = 0, Standard Deviation = 1). The criterion could take the value zero or one, where one indicated a positive case.

Definition of a Rule

A rule was defined as a vector of six values, referred to as beta-weights, $\langle a_1, a_2, \dots, a_6 \rangle$ which were used in the process of case selection.

Case Selection by the Rule

Cases were selected according to the following procedure:

1. For each of the five current cases calculate:
value $_k = a_1x_1 + a_2x_2 + \dots + a_6x_6$, where
 $\langle a_1, a_2, \dots, a_6 \rangle$ represented the rule R_1 .
2. Select the case for which value $_k$ was greatest, and add the case to the list L .

Construction of Rule R_{i+1}

The rule R_{i+1} was obtained by a linear regression analysis (Perlman, 1986). The case list L was entered for analysis and the output was of the form:

$$Y = a_1x_1 + a_2x_2 + \dots + a_6x_6$$

where a_k represents the weight of attribute x_k , such that the sum of the weighted attributes had the highest linear correlation with the criterion. The vector of α -weights $\langle a_1, a_2, \dots, a_6 \rangle$ obtained from the regression analysis constituted the new rule R_{i+1} . As a new case was added to L with each iteration of the learner, so the α -weights were revised to give the best linear estimate of the relationship between attributes $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_6$ and the criterion y .

As was mentioned earlier, a regression analysis was chosen for reasons of convenience. If another induction algorithm such as CART (Breiman, Friedman, Olshen & Stone, 1984) was employed then the nature of the induced relationship could vary; however, the fact that the induced relationship was an estimate of the relationship between attributes and the criterion would not change, and nor would the fact that the estimate effected the selection of subsequent cases.

The Databases

Four databases were constructed for this research. Each data database comprised 3000 cases, where the attribute values $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_6$ for the 3000 cases were identical across the four databases. The correlation between every attribute pair was low (ie: $r_{x_i, x_j} < .05$; where $i < j$). The databases differed only with respect to the manner in which the criterion was calculated for each case. Table 1 shows the generative rule employed to determine the criterion value, and the percentage of criterion values equal to one.

Insert Table 1 About Here

Initial Conditions

For a linear regression analysis to function it requires a minimum of n linearly independent cases for every n attributes. For this reason the case list L was seeded with 8 cases, rather than the minimum six because in small samples it is often difficult to ensure linear independence. There were essentially three possible choices to be made about the structure of the 8 initial cases:

1. The cases could have properly generated criterion values according to Table 1,
2. The cases could have incorrect criterion values, by allocating the opposite of the value expected according to Table 1.
3. The criterion values could be randomly assigned to each case, or

The advantage of the first approach was that the learner would not commence the simulation with false information. Unfortunately this would also give the learner an immediate and "unfair" advantage which could make determining the actual learning capacity of the simulation problematic. The second approach, and the one chosen in this study, was essentially to "lie" to the learner about what constituted a positive case. This put the learner at a maximal disadvantage initially, which meant no criticism could be made about "providing the learner with a friendly shove in the right direction" should the learner finally succeed. The third approach lacked either of the advantages of the first or second approach, and was consequently discounted.

The initial rule R_0 for each of the five experiments was calculated by inputting each of the five initial lists L into a regression analysis. The α -weights from these analyses constituted R_0 for each of the five simulations.

RESULTS

There are a number of ways in which the results of the simulations may be presented. They do, however, fall into two basic categories. The first category of results are those which reflect the proportion of positive cases selected by the learner. This category is of primary importance given that positive case selection is the principal aim of SeGuL. The second category is of those results which reflect iterative changes in the selection rule R , through the α -weights. This reflects the less important issue of whether the learner's model of the selected cases reflects the true underlying structure of the complete data-set. The proportion of positive cases will be presented first followed by the changes in the rule.

Proportion of Positive Cases

It should be kept in mind that the primary motivation for exploring the SeGul paradigm was not to examine the facility with which the learner could determine the underlying structure of the data set, rather it was to determine the facility with which the learner could select positive cases. Table 2 shows the percentage of positive cases in each of the data sets, the maximum number of positive cases that an optimal selection procedure could select, and the percentage of positive cases that the four different models actually did select. In no case could the optimal performance ever be expected to be 100%, because for each of the generative models there was always a probability that any one block of five cases would contain all negative cases. For the EW27 model, for example, there was a 73% chance that any one case was negative. This meant that in any block of five cases the probability that at least one of the cases would be positive was $1-(1-.27)^5 = .79$. In other words an optimal model could select only 79% positive cases.

Insert Table 2 About Here

Table 2 indicates that the equal weights models performed optimally, with increases above the base-rate from 19% to 51%. Unsurprisingly, the XOR model performed suboptimally, although it achieved a selection rate of positive cases 23% greater than that expected by chance alone. In view of the better than chance performance, it is worth spending a little time examining reasons why this may have been so.

The XOR generative model used arithmetic sums of attributes, $x_1+x_2+x_3$ and $x_4+x_5+x_6$. In order to moderate the difficulties of illustrating points in six-dimensional space, $x_1+x_2+x_3$ will be referred to by the single new attribute w_1 and $x_4+x_5+x_6$ will be referred to as w_2 . Now consider the two dimensional equivalent xor generative model employing the attributes w_1 and w_2 (Figure 3).

Insert Figures 3 About Here

A positive case in the two dimensional generative model is represented by the shaded portions of the upper-left and lower-right quadrants. The appropriate logical rule for positive case selection would be " $w_1 > 1.5$ xor $w_2 > 1.5$ ". Clearly there is no single line which could separate the positive case quadrants from the negative case quadrants; and herein lies the problem of linear models in coping with xor generative models. However, the purpose of the learner was not to generate a linear classifier which could deal with an XOR generative model, but to select positive cases.

The two dimensional rule analogous to the six dimensional rule employed in XOR learner's would be $\langle -0.12, 0.41 \rangle$. The logical rule equivalent of this is "IF w_2 is high AND NOT w_1 is high THEN select case as a positive case". This rule would, in effect, mean that the learner selected cases from the lower right quadrant and exclude the upper left quadrant. Table 3 shows the distribution of cases selected during the XOR simulation from the four quadrants: w_1 and $w_2 > 1.5$, w_1 and $w_2 < 1.5$, $w_1 > 1.5$ and $w_2 < 1.5$, and $w_1 < 1.5$ and $w_2 > 1.5$. The figures in italics represent the expected frequency of cases selected in each quadrant given only a random selection procedure, and the figures in bold represent the actual frequency of case selection in each quadrant.

Insert Table 3 About Here

It is apparent from the table that the first quadrant (a quadrant of positive cases) was over represented by more than a factor of three. Quadrant three on the other hand (another positive case quadrant) was under represented by a factor of 4.8. Clearly the learner has not achieved the impossible by generating a linear classifier which can deal with an XOR data-set; instead the learner has treated the data set as one containing only a single quadrant of positive cases. With each iteration of the learner, the list L of cases reflected the actual data-set less and less well, and a data set containing a single quadrant of positive cases better and better. The optimal selection rate (given equal distribution of positive cases between the two quadrants) that a linear learner could hope to achieve would be 50%; a figure very close to the actual 55% selection rate.

Changes in the Rule

Figures 4a to 4c show the changes in the values of the rules' α -weights over time for each of the equal weights models (EW50, EW27 and EW5). It can be seen that the α -weights for each of those models are converging to single values. This is consistent with the learner having induced the actual underlying equal weights relationship between the attributes and the criterion. In the EW27 and the EW5 models the α -weights had begun to converge by the 20th iteration, and even the EW50 model had begun to converge by the 100th iteration.

Similarly, figure 4d shows the changes in the values of the rules' α -weights over time for the XOR model. As can be seen from the graph, half the α -weights are converging to one value, and half the α -weights are converging to another. Further, it is the weights for attributes x_1 , x_2 , and x_3 which converge to one value, and attributes x_4 , x_5 , and x_6 which converge to the other. Table 1 shows that these two groups of attributes formed the two terms in the XOR model (and the composite attributes w_1 and w_2).

It is apparent that the weights for the XOR model had begun to converge toward two values by the 50th iteration.

Insert Figures 4a to 4d About Here

DISCUSSION

The aim of this study was to explore the facility with which a machine learner, employing a SeGuL learning paradigm, could select only positive cases from a data-set. The results of this study may be summed up very simply. The machine learner performed surprisingly well. In fact, the selection rate of positive cases by the learner was in three of the four simulations optimal. Those three simulations employed linear generative models, and as such we may be accused of having used a learner (a regression analysis) which was ready made for the task. This, however, would fail to give sufficient weight to the disadvantage that one might assume self guided learning would place on any learning system.

The fourth model, a generative XOR model, is known to be insoluble by a linear classifier. Notwithstanding that fact, the machine learner selected positive cases 55% of the time, when a random strategy could only select positive cases 32% of the time - an increase of 23%. This success seems to derive in part from the fact that the learner is not required to classify cases as positive or negative, but to select positive cases.

Although the explication of the underlying structure of the total data-set was of secondary importance, the learners for the three linear generative models did nonetheless reflect that structure in their rules for selecting positive cases. The learner for the XOR generative model on the other hand reflected a very different underlying data structure in its rules for selecting positive cases. Despite this failure the XOR learner still achieved a considerable success in selecting positive cases.

These results are surprising in virtue of a number of facts. Firstly, It is known that non random sampling strategies can bias a data-set, and such biases could radically effect inferences drawn on the basis of that sample (REFERENCE). Secondly, there is some evidence in the field of human judgement and decision making to suggest that the type of learning paradigm embodied in SeGuL would produce a view of reality which was not veridical, and was therefore suboptimal (Brehmer, 1980). Finally, there are a considerable number of philosophical works, particularly in the tradition of the British Empiricists, to suggest that induction generally is an undesirable strategy for selecting positive cases, and a self guided learning strategy would be particularly poor.

Inspite of this, machine implementations of SeGuL clearly perform better than chance at selecting positive cases, and in the event that the underlying data-structure suits the learning algorithm, it may perform optimally. What is particularly interesting about the success of the machine learner in this environment is that it may well out perform the human learner (Dawes & Corrigan, 1974). This has implications for a number of tasks such as screening insurance claims for fraud investigation (Reidpath, 1992), triaging patients in a hospital emergency department, selecting international passengers for baggage examination by Customs Officers (Reidpath & Diamond, 1992), and selecting personnel to fill job vacancies.

Given the initial success of this research, additional research focusing on self guided learning system, which can perform a task and continue learning on the run, seems warranted. Questions this research team is focusing its efforts on relate to the performance of tree algorithms, and neural networks in SeGuL tasks, as well as comparisons of machine learners with actual human performance.

Table 1: The names of the four databases, the rules for generating the criterion value (y) in each database, and the percentage of criterion values equal to 1 in each database.

Database	Rule	Percentage of positive cases
EW ₅₀	IF $x_1 + \dots + x_6 > 0$ THEN $y = 1$ ELSE $y = 0$	50
EW ₂₇	IF $x_1 + \dots + x_6 > 1.5$ THEN $y = 1$ ELSE $y = 0$	27
EW ₅	IF $x_1 + \dots + x_6 > 2.5$ THEN $y = 1$ ELSE $y = 0$	5
XOR	IF $x_1 + x_2 + x_3 > 1.5$ XOR $x_4 + x_5 + x_6 > 1.5$ THEN $y = 1$ ELSE $y = 0$	32

Table 2

Optimal positive case selection rate (OSR), the actual positive case selection rate (ASR), and the base rate of positive cases for each of the five learners: the three equal weights models (EW50, EW27, and EW5), and the logical exclusive or (XOR) model.

<u>Model</u>	<u>OSR</u>	<u>ASR</u>	<u>Base Rate</u>
EW50	97%	95%	50%
EW27	79%	78%	27%
EW5	23%	24%	5%
XOR	85%	55%	32%